

TEACHING CHALLENGES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION AND THEIR SOLUTIONS

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Annotation: *This article provides insights into reforms, challenges, and solutions in the preschool education system. Preschool education is the primary part of continuing education. It stimulates the child's desire to learn, prepares him for systematic learning, ensuring that he develops into a healthy and developed person. Therefore, the further strengthening of this system, the creation of all-round favorable conditions in preschool education institutions, the wide involvement of preschool children in them play an important role in the formation of our children as harmonious and mature individuals.*

Keywords: *translation strategy, language options, table storage, tutor.*

Introduction

"In general, the state requirements stipulate the development of young children and preschoolers in five areas. By developing these five areas, the child will have 4 competencies, he will be motivated to enter the 1st grade," said Agrippina Shin, Minister of Preschool Education of Uzbekistan.

Methods

The basis of everything in the new program is a social approach, that is, the focus is on the child and his interests. The educator creates a social environment with the parent, the pedagogical content, the child himself and, of course, social partners such as society and the state. In recent years, Uzbekistan has radically changed the system of preschool education in the country reform, revitalizing them, in particular, rebuilding them in a new context, is necessary for the system creating a new national model of the training process, the pedagogical process democratization, its liberalization and modernization, the process of education and upbringing clearly aimed at the introduction of modern innovations and advanced pedagogical technologies as well as large-scale work related to the development of the country's prospects.

Result

Particular importance of is the educational infrastructure of preschool education institutions to cover all children in our country in the process of

education and upbringing. Reorganization of preschool education organizations in the last four years and they radically change the practice, the mechanisms of financing the system about forty government documents, including Presidential Decrees and resolutions and orders of the Cabinet of Ministers, normative documents of the ministry accepted. In particular, the independent Ministry of Preschool Education of Uzbekistan has been established. The state on restructuring the activities of preschool educational institutions in our country further improvement of the system, strengthening its material and technical base, expanding the network of preschool education organizations, providing them with qualified teaching staff ensuring, radically improving the level of preparation of children for school education, education conditions for the application of modern educational programs and technologies in the process and the intellectual, moral, aesthetic, and physical development of children development has been identified as one of the most pressing tasks of our time.

Therefore, as the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev said, "Science, further improvement of the modern and continuing education system is needed. In our nation, There is a wise saying, "Education begins in the cradle." Only enlightenment perfects man, leads society to development. Therefore, public policy in the field of education is continuous education based on the principle of the system, that is, education should begin in kindergarten.

Discussions

The state is carrying out radical changes in the system of preschool education, its ideas and developing implementation mechanisms. The purpose of these changes to create all necessary pedagogical conditions, material and spiritual process of education and upbringing is to provide. As well as ensuring and implementing radical changes in the preschool education system for the development of primary and preschool children of the Republic of Uzbekistan State requirements were adopted. According to him, the preschool education system is responsible the tasks and requirements were clearly defined. Exact child opportunities development is one of the main goals of preschool education. "On further improvement of the preschool education system for 2017-2021 in preschool education institutions children social, personal, emotional, verbal, mathematical, physio-psychological, physical and creative. It is necessary to introduce educational programs for development. Because for the last 20 years the number of state-run preschools decreased by 45%. Through

this system. Only 33% of children in the country are covered. This indicator is advanced of the countries, 99 percent in Denmark, 97 percent in Japan, and 95 percent in South Korea. It is planned to carry out construction and repair work in the kindergarten at a cost of 771 billion soums funds allocated. Including methodological and didactic games, toys, plans to equip with furniture, equipment, ICT and technical means. In connection with the activities of preschool education organizations today, the following implementation of tasks, their monitoring, scientific conclusions on them and The development of recommendations is important and required:

1. Enhancing the role of the organization of preschool education in the state and society, the scientific and theoretical study of its content and essence to determine the current state of practice;

2. The concept of organizing the pedagogical process in preschool education pedagogical, psychological, medical, gender, spiritual-educational and gradual development of our country identify and analyze the characteristics specific to;

3. Organization of the process of education and upbringing in preschool educational institutions development of pedagogical and psychological bases;

4. Organization of the process of education and upbringing in preschool educational institutions development of effective forms, methods and ways and its innovative models and creation of technologies;

5. The state and in the organization of the process of education and upbringing in preschool educational institutions development of the basis for cooperation of non-governmental organizations;

6. Organization of the process of education and upbringing in preschool educational institutions create continuous monitoring and implementation in the system.

In short period, the activities of preschool education organizations in Uzbekistan are radically different. The process of reconstruction and its modern development has begun in a short period of time major changes have been made.

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